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The Editor-in-Chief

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Job characteristics, and the Influence of Gender and Educational Qualification on Marital Satisfaction of Married Working Individuals

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Abstract

This study investigated the predictive roles of five core job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback), and the influence of gender and educational qualification on marital satisfaction among married individuals in Ekiti State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was employed. A sample of 300 married individuals from Oye Local Government, Nigeria, completed measures on job characteristics (Job Characteristics Scale) and marital satisfaction (EMS Marital Satisfaction Scale). Data were analyzed using Pearson's correlation, multiple regression, one-way ANOVA, and an independent samples t-test. Multiple regression revealed that the combined job characteristics significantly predicted marital satisfaction ($R^2 = .05$, $F_{(5, 296)} = 4.60$, $p < .01$), with skill variety ($\beta = .18$, $p < .01$) and autonomy ($\beta = .274$, $p < .05$) emerging as independent significant predictors. A significant gender difference was found ($t_{(299)} = 3.66$, $p < .05$), with men reporting higher marital satisfaction than women. Educational level did not significantly influence marital satisfaction. The findings underscore that certain empowering job characteristics, particularly autonomy and skill variety, are positively associated with marital satisfaction. The study imply that organizations are encouraged to design jobs that offer discretion and variety to support family well-being especially for male employees.

Keywords: Job Characteristics, Marital Satisfaction, Gender, Educational qualification

Introduction

Marriage involves the coming together of two different individuals with different view-points on varying issues to cohabit under the same roof. It thus suffices to say that there is bound to be a conflict of individual differences between both spouses at regular intervals. However, the ability to accommodate these differences is a reflection of the pivot that holds the stability of the union and the satisfaction of the spouse with the marriage (Umukoro, 2011). In every society, every individual is expected to face certain challenges in marriage. These challenges could lead to serious marital dissatisfaction if not well managed. Achieving marital satisfaction in a marriage has become one of the most prevalent and endemic social challenges ravaging many families and communities in Nigeria. Since the family is the bedrock on which every society is built, the question of achieving national stability must first be addressed from the family unit with special reference to conflicts in marriages.

According to Sholfer and Shoben (2014) marital relationships experience crisis and conflicts that sometimes result in divorce, separation, broken homes, violence against women or men, child neglect and several other devastating effects of intra-marital conflicts. Marital satisfaction is a critical determinant of family stability, individual mental health, and societal well-being (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023; Olagundoye et al., 2020; Olagundoye et al., 2019). In Nigeria, as in many developing nations, marital instability and dissatisfaction pose significant social problems, often linked to psychological distress, financial strain, and poor communication (Fagbenro & Olagundoye, 2019). While a multitude of factors influence marital quality, the spillover effects from the work domain are particularly salient in an era where occupational demands increasingly intrude upon family life (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023).

The Job Characteristics Model (JCM) (Hackman & Oldham, 1976) provides a robust framework for understanding how work design impacts employee motivation and well-being. The model posits that five core characteristics skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback influence critical psychological states, leading to positive personal and work outcomes. While extensively applied to job performance and satisfaction (Omole et al., 2019), its application to family outcomes is less common. According to the Work-Home Resources Model (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023), job resources like autonomy and skill variety can generate positive energy and functional skills that may be transferred to the home domain, thereby enriching marital interactions.

Preliminary evidence suggests a link between job characteristics and marital quality. For instance, jobs high in autonomy may reduce work-family conflict by granting employees flexibility to manage family demands (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023). Similarly, skill variety and task significance can enhance self-efficacy, which may positively affect one's role as a spouse (Carlson et al., 2019). However, the literature is fragmented, with mixed findings and a predominant focus on Western contexts (Heller et al., 2004; Karney & Bradbury, 2005), underscoring the need for research in different cultural and economic settings like Nigeria, where work and family dynamics are uniquely shaped by socio-cultural norms.

Beyond work factors, demographic variables like gender and education are pivotal. A consistent global finding is that men often report higher marital satisfaction than women (Arowosegbe et al., 2019), a disparity often attributed to gendered role expectations and the "second shift" experienced by employed women. The influence of education, however, remains ambiguous, with some studies suggesting it fosters egalitarian values and communication skills that benefit marriage (Sullivan et al., 2018), while others find no direct link (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023).

This study aims to address these gaps by examining the predictive role of the five JCM characteristics and gender on marital satisfaction within a Nigerian sample. The findings contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the work-marriage interface in a non-Western context and inform both organizational practices and family support interventions.

Hypotheses

1. The five job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback) will jointly and independently predict marital satisfaction.
2. There will be no significant difference in marital satisfaction based on participants' educational level.
3. There will be a significant gender difference in marital satisfaction, with men reporting higher satisfaction than women.

Methods

Participants and Procedure

A cross-sectional survey design was employed. Using a convenience sampling technique, 300 married individuals employed within Oye Local Government Area, Ekiti State, Nigeria, were recruited. Participants were approached at their workplaces and provided informed consent

after the study's purpose was explained. Ethical approval was granted by the Institutional Review Board of the Federal University Oye Ekiti. Participants completed a sociodemographic questionnaire, the Job Characteristics Scale, and the Marital Satisfaction Scale.

Measures

Marital Satisfaction: The 15-item ENRICH Marital Satisfaction (EMS) Scale (Fowers & Olson, 1993) was used. Respondents indicate their agreement on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). A sample item is, "My partner completely understands and sympathizes with my every mood." Higher scores indicate greater marital satisfaction. The scale demonstrated excellent reliability in this study (Cronbach's $\alpha = .92$).

Job Characteristics: The Job Characteristics Scale (JCS) by Hackman and Oldham (1975) was used. It measures five dimensions and the five core dimensions was used analyzed: skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback. Responses are recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = Very Inaccurate to 7 = Very Accurate). The subscales showed acceptable to good reliability in the current sample (Skill Variety $\alpha = .72$; Autonomy $\alpha = .70$; Feedback $\alpha = .68$; Task Identity $\alpha = .65$; Task Significance $\alpha = .63$).

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics were computed for all variables. Pearson Moment Correlation was used to test the relationship among study variables. Hypothesis 1 was tested using multiple regression analysis. Hypothesis 2 was tested using a one-way ANOVA, and Hypothesis 3 was tested using an independent samples t-test.

Results

Relationships among variables

Table 1: Correlation Matrix Showing Relationship between Variables in the Study

S/N	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Skill Variety	-	.73**	.87**	.73**	.81**	.61**	.01
2	Task Identity		-	.71**	.64**	.76**	.05	-.07
3	Task Significance			-	.80**	.72*	.15*	.04
4	Autonomy				-	.86**	.53**	.27**
5	Feedback					-	.28**	.30
6	Marital Satisfaction						-	.36**
7	Age							-

Result from Table 1 reveals the interrelationship among variables of the study tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The dimensions of job characteristics were significantly positively correlated with one another. Further, marital satisfaction had a significant positive relationship with skill variety ($r = .61, p < .01$), task significance ($r = .15, p < .05$), autonomy ($r = .53, p < .01$), feedback ($r = .28, p < .01$) and age ($r = .36, p < .01$). This means that marital satisfaction increases when skill variety, task significance autonomy and feedback increases. The relationship of marital satisfaction with task identity was however not significant ($r = .05, p > .05$).

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis one states that job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy and feedback) will significantly predict marital satisfaction. This was tested with multiple regression analysis as presented in Table 2

Table 2: Multiple Regression Summary Table showing job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy and feedback) as predictors of Marital Satisfaction

Criterion	Predictors	β	t	P	R ²	F	P
Marital Satisfaction	Skill Variety	0.17	4.87	<.01	.05	4.60	<.05
	Task Identity	0.12	1.64	>.05			
	Task Significance	0.01	0.09	>.05			
	Autonomy	0.27	3.00	<.05			
	Feedback	0.08	0.98	>.05			

Result from Table 2 reveal that job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy and feedback) significantly jointly predicted marital satisfaction [(R² = .05; F_(5, 296) = 4.60; p <.01)]. This means that job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy and feedback) accounts for about 5.2% of the variation observed in marital satisfaction. Only the independent contribution of skill variety ($\beta = .18$; t = 4.88; p <.01) and autonomy ($\beta = .27$; t = 3.00; p <.05) were significant in the model. Hence, the stated hypothesis is partially accepted.

Hypothesis two stated that more educated participants will be significantly more satisfied maritally than those less educated. This was tested with one way analysis of variance as presented in Table 3

Table 3: One-way ANOVA Summary Table Showing influence of Education on Marital Satisfaction

	Source	SS	DF	MS	F-ratio	p
Marital Satisfaction	Between groups	1987.48	4	196.87	2.15	>.05
	Within Groups	10468.46	311	21.16		
	Total	12455.94	315			

Result from Table 3 showed that participant's educational level has no significant influence on the marital satisfaction of participants F_(4, 311) = 2.15, p >.05). The stated hypothesis is not confirmed.

Hypothesis three states that there will be significant gender differences in the marital satisfaction of participants. This was tested with an independent sample t-test as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: t-test Showing gender differences in Marital Satisfaction

DV	Gender	N	X	SD	df	t	p
Marital Satisfaction	Male	192	34.07	3.06	298	3.65	<.05
	Female	109	29.56	3.03			

Results from Table 4 reveals that there is a significant gender difference in the marital satisfaction of participants ($t_{(298)} = 3.65, p < .05$). Further observation of means reveals that male participants ($X=34.07, S.D=3.06$) were more satisfied with their marriages than female participants ($X=29.56, S.D=3.03$). The hypothesis stated is confirmed.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the predictive roles of job characteristics and gender on marital satisfaction in a Nigerian sample. The findings partially support our first hypothesis. While the combination of job characteristics significantly predicted marital satisfaction, only skill variety and autonomy emerged as significant unique predictors. This suggests that jobs offering employees a range of challenges and the freedom to determine how to perform their work are most strongly associated with positive spillover into marital life. This aligns with the Work-Home Resources Model (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023), as autonomy and variety are key resources that can reduce strain and foster a sense of competence that benefits interpersonal relationships at home (Tang et al., 2021). The non-significant unique contributions of task identity, task significance, and feedback suggest that while these factors are important for job-related outcomes, their direct transfer to the marital domain in this specific context may be less potent than the psychological empowerment derived from autonomy and variety.

Supporting our second hypothesis, educational level was not a significant predictor of marital satisfaction. This finding challenge simplistic assumptions that higher education directly translates to better marriages and suggests that the quality of the relationship and other contextual factors are more critical determinants (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023). The most robust finding was the significant gender gap in marital satisfaction, with men reporting

higher levels than women. This is consistent with a global body of literature (e.g., Jackson et al., 2014) and can be contextualized within the Nigerian socio-cultural milieu. Despite increasing female workforce participation, women often retain primary responsibility for domestic labor and childcare (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023). This "double burden" can lead to role overload and chronic stress, diminishing marital quality. Furthermore, patriarchal norms may lead to unequal power dynamics within the household, constraining women's voice and satisfaction (Olagundoye & Odunjo-Saka, 2023).

Conclusion

This research demonstrates that job design, particularly the degree of autonomy and skill variety it offers, is significantly linked to marital satisfaction. Furthermore, it reaffirms the persistent gender gap in marital quality, underscoring the need for societal and policy-level changes to address unequal domestic burdens. Fostering empowering work environments and promoting gender equity at home are dual pathways toward enhancing marital satisfaction and, by extension, societal health.

Implication

Theoretically, this study extends the JCM and the Work-Home Resources Model by demonstrating their relevance to marital outcomes in a non-Western context. Practically, the findings suggest that organizational leaders and HR professionals can contribute to employee well-being beyond the workplace by designing jobs that are enriching and offer flexibility. Initiatives such as flexible working hours, remote work options, and employee autonomy programs could indirectly support marital stability. For clinicians and counselors, these results highlight the importance of considering occupational context and gender roles when addressing marital discord.

Limitation and Future Research

This study has several limitations. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences. The use of convenience sampling limits the generalizability of the findings. Self-report data may be susceptible to common method bias. Future research should employ longitudinal designs, more diverse and representative samples, and include dyadic data from both spouses. Investigating mediating mechanisms (e.g., psychological empowerment, work-family conflict) and moderating variables (e.g., spousal support, cultural norms) would provide a deeper understanding of the underlying processes

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